

Some new furanones : Synthesis, characterisation and antimicrobial activity

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Abstract : The synthesis of some new furanones starting from three γ -keto acids, β -(3,4-dimethylbenzoyl)acrylic acid, β -(2,4-dimethylbenzoyl)acrylic acid and β -(2,5-dimethylbenzoyl)acrylic acid is described. Each acid is condensed with various phenols using catalytic quantity of sulphuric acid as condensing agent to get the furanones. The structures of synthesized compounds have been elucidated by elemental analysis, spectral data and chemical reactions. Some of the synthesized compounds have been evaluated for their antimicrobial activities also.

Keywords : Furanones, antimicrobial activity, phenols.

Introduction

Furanones constitute an important group of α,β -unsaturated five membered γ -lactones, which are often referred to as $\Delta^{\alpha\beta}$ -butenolides. Recent years have witnessed a marked upsurge in the chemistry of furanones because of their potential biological properties and wide ranging occurrence in natural products¹. There is enormous interest in the development of convenient and efficient methodologies for the synthesis of furanones because they are attractive building blocks in natural product synthesis^{2,3} and comprise structural moieties present in large number of significant compounds, e.g. insect pheromones⁴, cardinolides⁵, lignans⁶, flavour components⁷ and large number of synthetic drugs associated with potential biological properties⁸⁻¹³. It has been observed that furanones are often encountered among fungi¹⁴, bacteria¹⁵ and gorgonians¹⁶ etc. The saturated analogues of these unsaturated lactones have been reported to act as signalling substances in bacteria¹⁷ and enhance spore formation in streptomycetes or induce metabolite production¹⁵. The reactivity of γ -lactone ring of furanones has been successfully utilized for the synthesis of nitrogen heterocycles of potential pharmaceutical significance^{19,20}. More recently, some new furanones have been prepared and reacted with ammonia and benzylamine to give corresponding pyrrolones and *N*-benzylpyrrolones, respectively²¹.

The continued interest in the chemistry of furanones resulted in some recent publications^{22,23} in this area describing the use of green methods for their synthesis. These significant observations gave an impetus to synthesize a group of new furanones (4-11) by a simple and convenient procedure employing easily accessible and inexpensive chemicals and test the possibility of antibacterial and antifungal activities in some of the synthesized compounds. The results of this study are being communicated in this paper.

Results and discussion

In the present work we have condensed three γ -keto acids, β -(3,4-dimethylbenzoyl)acrylic acid (1a), β -(2,4-dimethylbenzoyl)acrylic acid (1b) and β -(2,5-dimethylbenzoyl)acrylic acid (1c) with various mono-, di- and trihydroxy phenols (3) in presence of catalytic quantity of concentrated sulphuric acid to get the new furanones (4-9). The furanones 5a, 5b, 5c on acetylation and bromination gave their corresponding diacetyl derivatives (10a, 10b, 10c) and dibromo derivatives (11a, 11b, 11c), respectively. The acids (1a, 1b, 1c) reacted with phenols (3) through their cyclic lactol tautomeric forms (2a, 2b, 2c) as depicted in Scheme 1. The occurrence of keto-lactol tautomerism in γ -keto and γ -formyl acids, and their participation in some reactions through their cyclic lactol

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- (4) $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = H$; $R_3 = OH$ (8) $R_2 = R_4 = H$; $R_1 = R_3 = R_5 = OH$ (1-11) (a) $R'_2 = R'_3 = CH_3$; $R'_1 = H$
 (5) $R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = H$; $R_1 = R_3 = OH$ (9) $R_4 = R_5 = H$; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = OH$ (b) $R'_1 = R'_2 = CH_3$; $R'_3 = H$
 (6) $R_1 = R_4 = R_5 = H$; $R_2 = R_3 = OH$ (10) $R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = H$; $R_1 = R_3 = OCOCH_3$ (c) $R'_1 = R'_3 = CH_3$; $R'_2 = H$
 (7) $R_2 = R_3 = R_5 = H$; $R_1 = R_4 = OH$ (11) $R_5 = H$; $R_2 = R_4 = Br$; $R_1 = R_3 = OH$

Scheme 1

form is well documented^{22,24}. In the synthesized furanones, carbon-5 of furanone ring is attached to two different phenyl rings, one being phenolic and the other non-phenolic containing two methyl groups. Thus, these compounds may be regarded as unsymmetrically substituted furanones. Their structures are established by elemental analysis, UV, IR, NMR and Mass spectral data.

All the synthesized furanones (4-11) in their IR spectra (in KBr, ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) showed two sharp and strong bands in the region 1790–1760 and 1755–1730 cm^{-1} , which are characteristic of five membered α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone ring (ν_{CO}). A prominent peak noticed at 1620–1610 cm^{-1} is assignable to olefinic double bond ($\nu_{C=C}$) present in furanone ring. UV spectra (in methanol) revealed the presence of two absorption bands at 230–270 and 275–310 nm. In the 1H NMR spectra (in DMSO- d_6) of the furanones, α -olefinic proton appeared as a doublet at δ 6.00–6.25 while β -olefinic proton and aromatic protons formed a complex multiplet in the region between δ 6.90–8.20. The representative furanone 5a was subjected to mass spectral analysis to confirm the proposed structures on the basis of fragmentation pattern and molecular weight obtained from molecular ion. The mass spectrum shows a clear molecular ion at m/z 296 together with a base peak at m/z 133. The other prominent mass ion peaks present in the mass spectrum are at m/z (rel. int.) 252 (10), 251 (47), 163 (25), 162 (25), 105 (41), 79 (21) and 77 (25).

Antimicrobial activity :

Some of synthesized furanones, 4a, 4b, 4c, 5a, 5b, 5c, 10a, 10b, 10c, 11a, 11b, 11c, were screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity against four bacteria (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus coli*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and four fungi (*Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Candida albicans* and *Fusarium oxysporum*) by agar well diffusion assay. All the selected compounds were dissolved in 80% ethanol and their antimicrobial activity was tested at a concentration of 100 $\mu g/mL$ using Chloramphenicol and Amphotericin B as standard for antibacterial and antifungal activity, respectively. The activity was recorded as zone of inhibition (measured in mm) from the edge of the zone to the edge of the well after 24 h incubation (at 24 °C for fungi and 37 °C for bacteria). Fungal and bacterial suspensions were prepared in sabourauds dextrose and nutrients broths, respectively. Results of the assay are presented in Table 1. A critical examination of these results indicates that the synthesized furanones exhibit antifungal as well as antibacterial activities. On acetylation and bromination of furanones there is remarkable enhancement in the antimicrobial activity while position of methyl groups and number of hydroxyl groups have no significant influence on antibacterial or antifungal activity.

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of some synthesized furanones
Zone of inhibition (mm) (activity index)^a

Compd.	Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity			
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. coli</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>F. oxysporum</i>
4a	10 (0.40)	16 (0.50)	15 (0.53)	12 (0.40)	4 (0.40)	7 (0.46)	3 (0.30)	6 (0.50)
4b	11 (0.44)	18 (0.56)	15 (0.53)	16 (0.53)	5 (0.50)	4 (0.26)	4 (0.40)	5 (0.41)
4c	10 (0.40)	15 (0.46)	18 (0.64)	16 (0.53)	4 (0.40)	8 (0.53)	4 (0.40)	5 (0.41)
5a	12 (0.48)	12 (0.37)	16 (0.57)	14 (0.46)	4 (0.40)	7 (0.46)	5 (0.50)	4 (0.33)
5b	10 (0.40)	14 (0.43)	14 (0.50)	15 (0.50)	3 (0.30)	6 (0.40)	4 (0.40)	5 (0.41)
5c	13 (0.52)	15 (0.46)	19 (0.67)	17 (0.56)	5 (0.50)	7 (0.46)	5 (0.50)	4 (0.33)
10a	16 (0.64)	19 (0.59)	20 (0.71)	21 (0.70)	7 (0.70)	8 (0.53)	6 (0.60)	8 (0.66)
10b	13 (0.52)	18 (0.56)	27 (0.96)	20 (0.66)	6 (0.60)	10 (0.66)	7 (0.70)	9 (0.75)
10c	15 (0.60)	30 (0.93)	22 (0.78)	20 (0.66)	8 (0.66)	9 (0.60)	8 (0.80)	6 (0.50)
11a	25 (1.00)	30 (0.93)	25 (0.89)	24 (0.80)	10 (1.80)	12 (0.80)	9 (0.90)	8 (0.66)
11b	26 (1.04)	26 (0.81)	29 (1.03)	28 (0.93)	10 (1.00)	18 (1.20)	10 (1.00)	12 (1.00)
11c	20 (0.80)	25 (0.78)	28 (1.00)	25 (0.83)	9 (0.90)	10 (0.66)	11 (1.10)	14 (1.16)
Chloramphenicol	25	32	28	30	-	-	-	-
Amphotericin B	-	-	-	-	10	15	10	12

^aActivity index = Zone of inhibition of the compound/Zone of inhibition of the standard.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian FT-80A spectrometer using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent (chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm relative to TMS as internal standard). UV spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 15 UV/Vis spectrophotometer and mass spectrum on a GC-MS instrument. TLC was used to access the reactions and ascertain the purity of the synthesized compounds. For TLC plates coated with alumina silica gel G (1 : 1) layers were run in petroleum ether (b.p. 40–70 °C)-acetone (60 : 40, v : v).

β-(3,4-Dimethylbenzoyl)acrylic acid (1a), β-(2,4-dimethylbenzoyl)acrylic acid (1b) and β-(2,5-dimethylbenzoyl)acrylic acid (1c) were prepared by Friedel-Crafts acylation of *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene and *p*-xylene, respectively by maleic anhydride in presence of anhydrous AlCl₃ following the literature procedures^{25,26}. The phenols used were phenol, resorcinol, catechol, quinol, phloroglucinol and pyrogallol and they were taken in slight excess over the acid (1).

Synthesis of 5-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-5-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-furanone (5a) : The acid β-(2,3-dimethylbenzoyl)acrylic acid (4.08 g, 20 mmol) was well dried and intimately mixed with resorcinol (2.53 g, 23 mmol), and the resulting mixture was heated to 120 °C to get a

homogeneous solution. Thereafter, concentrated sulphuric acid (4 drops) was added and heating was continued at 120–130 °C for 3 h to get a hard and brittle mass on cooling. It was washed thoroughly with water to remove excess of the resorcinol, extracted with 2% aqueous sodium hydroxide and filtered. The filtrate was cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid to get the furanone (5a) as a dark brown sticky solid mass. It was purified by column chromatography on a silica gel column using benzene-ethanol (80 : 20) as eluent. The eluted furanone was crystallized from aqueous ethanol as a reddish brown microcrystalline compound (4.1 g, 69%), m.p. 170–172 °C, IR : ν 3407, 1780, 1760, 1618 cm⁻¹; UV (MeOH) : λ_{max} 270, 295 nm; ¹H NMR (80 MHz) : δ 6.20 (1H, d, α-olefinic proton), 6.60–7.95 (7H, m, β-olefinic proton and aromatic protons), 4.50 (2H, br s, 2 × Ar-OH), 2.20, 2.30 (each as 3H, s, 2 × CH₃); MS : *m/z* (rel. int.) 296 (M⁺, 14), 252 (10), 251 (47), 163 (25), 162 (25), 133 (100), 105 (41), 79 (21) and 77 (25) (Found : C, 73.21; H, 5.72. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₆O₄ : C, 72.97; H, 5.41 %).

The other furanones were synthesized as brownish white to brown microcrystalline solids in 60 to 70% yield following the procedure described above. Their characterization data are given below :

4a : Brownish white microcrystals, m.p. 166–167 °C (Found : C, 77.25; H, 6.06. C₁₈H₁₆O₃ requires : C, 77.14;

H, 6.01%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 260, 310 nm; IR : 3420, 1790, 1730, 1612 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz): δ 2.20, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 5.60 (1H, brs), 6.15 (1H, d), 6.85–8.10 (8H, m).

4b : Brownish white microcrystals, m.p. 162–163 °C (Found : C, 76.54; H, 5.98. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 77.14; H, 6.01%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 242, 300 nm; IR : 3400, 1780, 1750, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.15, 2.35 (each 3H, s), 6.00 (1H, br s) 6.20 (1H, d), 6.90–7.95 (8H, m).

4c : Brown microcrystals, m.p. 129–130 °C (Found : C, 76.90; H, 5.84. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 77.14; H, 6.01%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 260, 310 nm; IR : 3415, 1780, 1740, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 4.50 (1H, br s), 6.10 (1H, d), 6.75–8.00 (8H, m).

5b : Reddish brown microcrystalline solid, m.p. 170–172 °C (Found : C, 72.80; H, 5.12. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 72.97; H, 5.41%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 260, 290 nm; IR : 3380, 1790, 1750, 1615 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 4.50 (2H, br s), 6.00 (1H, d), 6.85–8.10 (7H, m).

5c : Brownish red microcrystalline compound, m.p. 240–242 °C (Found : C, 72.72; H, 5.06. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 72.92; H, 5.41%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 250, 210 nm; IR : 3370, 1785, 1730, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.25, 2.35 (each 3H, s), 4.50 (2H, br s), 6.10 (1H, d), 6.90–8.15 (7H, m).

6a : Light brown microcrystals, m.p. 244–246 °C (Found : C, 72.77; H, 5.38. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 72.97; H, 5.41%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 260, 300 nm; IR : 3400, 1780, 1750, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.15, 2.25 (each 3H, s), 5.20 (2H, br s), 6.20 (1H, d), 6.90–8.00 (7H, m).

6b : Light brown microcrystals, m.p. 280–282 °C (Found : C, 73.21; H, 5.42. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 72.97; H, 5.41%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 240, 280 nm; IR : 3400, 1790, 1755, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.12, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 5.50 (2H, br s), 6.20 (1H, d), 6.75–7.90 (7H, m).

6c : Brown microcrystalline solid, m.p. 218–220 °C (Found : C, 73.13; H, 5.38. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 72.97; H, 5.41%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 260, 300 nm; IR : 3400, 1780, 1750, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20,

2.30 (each 3H, s), 4.50 (2H, br s), 6.15 (1H, d), 6.50–7.85 (7H, m).

7a : Brownish yellow microcrystals, m.p. 215–217 °C (Found : C, 73.81; H, 5.52. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 72.97; H, 5.41%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 260, 300 nm; IR : 3450, 1780, 1750, 1615 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 5.00 (2H, br s), 6.20 (1H, d), 6.90–7.85 (7H, m).

7b : Brownish yellow microcrystals, m.p. 210–212 °C (Found : C, 72.77; H, 5.32. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 72.97; H, 5.41%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 240, 280 nm; IR : 3420, 1790, 1750, 1615 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.15, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 5.00 (2H, br s), 6.15 (1H, d), 6.60–7.90 (7H, m).

7c : Brown microcrystalline solid, m.p. 233–235 °C (Found : C, 72.63; H, 5.43. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 72.97; H, 5.41%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 260, 300 nm; IR : 3450, 1780, 1730, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20, 2.35 (each 3H, s), 4.80 (2H, br s), 6.15 (1H, d), 6.50–7.90 (7H, m).

8a : Dark orange microcrystalline solid, m.p. 230–232 °C (Found : C, 68.95; H, 5.11. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 69.23; H, 5.12%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 260, 280 nm; IR : 3400, 1790, 1750, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.21, 2.35 (each 3H, s), 4.60 (3H, br s), 6.20 (1H, d), 6.70–7.85 (6H, m).

8b : Dark orange microcrystalline solid, m.p. 200–202 °C (Found : C, 69.40; H, 5.18. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 69.23; H, 5.12%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 240, 300 nm; IR : 3400, 1790, 1740, 1615 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.21, 2.35 (each 3H, s), 5.00 (2H, br s), 6.20 (1H, d), 6.70–7.80, (6H, m).

8c : Reddish brown microcrystalline solid, m.p. > 300 °C (Found : C, 69.15; H, 5.26. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 69.23; H, 5.12%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 260, 300 nm; IR : 3400, 1785, 1730, 1615 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.21, 2.35 (each 3H, s), 5.20 (3H, br s), 6.15 (1H, d), 6.65–8.10 (6H, m).

9a : Dark brown microcrystalline compound, m.p. > 300 °C (Found : C, 69.11; H, 5.03. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 69.23; H, 5.12%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{\max} 260, 300 nm; IR : 3400, 1790, 1755, 1620 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 5.50 (3H, br s), 6.10 (1H, d), 6.75–8.10 (6H, m).

9b : Dark brown microcrystalline compound, m.p. 243–245 °C (Found : C, 69.45; H, 5.80. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires : C, 69.23; H, 5.12%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{max} 230, 275 nm; IR : 3410, 1790, 1740, 1615 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 5.50 (3H, br s), 6.10 (1H, d), 6.70–7.95 (6H, m).

9c : Brown microcrystals, m.p. 291–293 °C (Found : C, 69.27; H, 5.07. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires : C, 69.23; H, 5.12%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{max} 260, 300 nm; IR : 3420, 1780, 1740, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 5.20 (3H, br s), 6.10 (1H, d), 6.70–7.95 (6H, m).

Acetylation of furanones 5a, 5b, 5c : The furanone **5a** or **5b** or **5c** (1.0 g) was mixed with acetic anhydride (15 mL) and freshly fused sodium acetate (3.0 g) and the mixture was refluxed at 130–140 °C for 3 h to get diacetyl derivative **11a** or **11b** or **11c**. The acetyl derivative was chromatographed on silica gel column using 10% acetone in petroleum ether as eluent. The eluted compound **10a** or **10b** or **10c** was crystallized from acetone.

10a : Yellowish white microcrystals (0.6 g), m.p. 240–242 °C (Found : C, 69.87; H, 5.30. $C_{22}H_{20}O_6$ requires : C, 69.47; H, 5.26%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{max} 260, 280 nm; IR : 1760, 1740, 1618 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 2.40 (6H, s), 6.20 (1H, d), 6.60–8.00 (7H, m).

10b : Yellowish white microcrystals (0.8 g), m.p. 263–265 °C (Found : C, 69.23; H, 5.18. $C_{22}H_{20}O_6$ requires : C, 69.47; H, 5.26%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{max} 240, 300 nm; IR : 1760, 1740, 1620 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.15, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 2.40 (6H, s), 6.15 (1H, d), 6.80–8.10 (7H, m).

10c : Reddish yellow microcrystals (0.7 g), m.p. 128–130 °C (Found : C, 69.49; H, 5.13. $C_{22}H_{20}O_6$ requires : C, 69.47; H, 5.26%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{max} 250, 300 nm; IR : 1770, 1750, 1615 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.10, 2.20 (each 3H, s), 2.50 (6H, s), 6.20 (1H, d), 6.60–7.80 (7H, m).

Bromination of furanones 5a, 5b, 5c : The furanone **5a** or **5b** or **5c** (1.0 g) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (15 mL). A 10% solution of bromine in glacial acetic acid (10 mL) was added to it gradually with stirring and cooling. The contents on dilution with water gave the

dark brown dibromo compound **11a** or **11b** or **11c**. These were chromatographed on a column of silica gel using benzene-ethanol (80 : 20) as eluent. The eluted solid was crystallized from acetic acid.

11a : Brick-red microcrystals (1.1 g), m.p. > 300 °C (Found : C, 47.80; H, 3.12; Br, 35.36. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4Br_2$ requires : C, 47.57; H, 3.08; Br, 35.24%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{max} 260, 300 nm; IR : 3440, 1780, 1755, 1611 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 5.30 (2H, br s), 6.25 (1H, d), 6.90–8.20 (5H, m).

11b : Reddish brown microcrystalline compound (1.3 g), m.p. 245–248 °C (Found : C, 47.39; H, 3.10; Br, 35.21. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4Br_2$ requires : C, 47.57; H, 3.08; Br, 35.24%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{max} 245, 300 nm; IR : 3400, 1780, 1740, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.20, 2.30 (each 3H, s), 5.50 (2H, br s), 6.10 (1H, d), 6.90–8.10 (5H, m).

11c : Brown microcrystals (0.8 g), m.p. 259–261 °C (Found : C, 47.68; H, 3.06; Br, 35.18. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4Br_2$ requires : C, 47.57; H, 3.08; Br, 35.24%); UV (MeOH) : λ_{max} 260, 300 nm; IR : 3450, 1780, 1740, 1610 cm^{-1} ; PMR (80 MHz) : δ 2.25, 2.35 (each 3H, s), 5.60 (2H, br s), 6.10 (1H, d), 6.90–8.10 (5H, m).

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